

THE PROCESS OF WHEAT GRAIN COMBINED WITH HEAT AND ITS INFLUENCE ON THE QUALITY INDICATORS OF WHEAT GRAIN

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Abstract. *It is known that native starches of wheat grain are converted into modified starch during heat treatment. The content of sugar and dextrins increases 2-3 times, the level of crystallization reaches 35% and higher. Research results show that replacing animal feed with "processed" wheat has a positive effect on the growth of animals, their productivity increases.*

Organization of research on improving the processing of grain products on a scientific basis ensures further increase in the efficiency of production in agriculture. This article shows the increase in quality indicators of grain products by processing them in a combined method.

Keywords: *dispersion, combined method, hydrothermal, urease, micronization, extrusion, microwave.*

Methodology of the experiment: The efficiency of processing methods depends on the compliance with the appropriate wheat processing technology. This conclusion is very important, because the quality of protein is adversely affected by overheating of raw materials, as well as the heating time of wheat grain.

When choosing a wheat grain processing method, it is necessary to determine the parameters of moisture and heat effects, as well as to determine whether technicians can control all parameters in a way that prevents optimal quality and low-quality products, and focus on reducing production costs.

In order to control the quality management of hydrothermal processing of wheat, it is necessary to use quick data on urease activity, protein dispersion indicator.

To this end, one of the research tasks was to develop the cheapest technological methods that would reduce the anti-nutritional factors in wheat seed and at the same time make the nutrients of the resulting feed as accessible as possible to livestock, and this was done. The main thermal treatment of the seeds is achieved using only infrared (IR) heating and the combined method of heating (KU) pre-soaked wheat seeds.

In order to study the effect of energy parameters of heat treatment on the reduction of urease level in wheat grain, studies on dynamic processes were carried out, including: heating of wheat, the effect of different heat flow intensities and duration of treatment during micronization and combined heat and power supply were determined.

First, the wheat grain was weighed to obtain equal weights, and then soaked to the same moisture content in all samples.

In order to determine the moisture with high accuracy, since this process required a considerable amount of time, the moisture was measured and sampled before processing and sent to the laboratory with the remaining samples.

In order to conduct research, IR radiation with a certain power was installed on the experimental sample. The light power of the IR radiation was fed through a circuit breaker. To

obtain temperature data and temperature differences in the upper, lower and central parts of the grain, sensors were placed directly on the upper, middle and lower parts of the grain. Since it is not possible to use such a series of sensors to measure one grain parameter and place the sensors, the measurements were carried out in different experiments with the same processing parameters.

Temperature monitoring and dynamic indicators were recorded at intervals of 5 seconds from the start of the calculation until the grain temperature reached 110-150 degrees. After intensive heat treatment, the wheat grain was poured into a pre-prepared heat-insulated container, where it underwent a hot-cold process (hardening) for 15 minutes. Duration of tempering was observed based on our research results and data of various authors. After tempering, the samples were sent to the chemical laboratory to determine urease activity and initial moisture content of wheat grain. The data obtained on heating dynamics were formed in the tables of relative strength, processing time and relative heat flow. As a quality indicator of the above parameters, the dependence of the effect on urease activity has also been established [1]. [4.5,4.6]

1. Results of the experiment. To evaluate the usefulness and adequacy of heat treatment in heated wheat samples, the following grain quality indicators were determined:

1. Urease activity (AU) as an official criterion of the degree of inhibition of anti-nutritional factors in processed wheat according to GOST 13979-urease. The optimal level of hydrothermal treatment is around AY 0,1- 0,3 Δ pH;

2. Water protein dispersion index (IDP). IDP is a test indicator of the adequacy of hydrothermal testing of wheat, in which nutrients are inactivated while maintaining high protein digestibility;

3. The IDP indicator was expressed as a percentage of the separated fraction of water-soluble protein to the total protein content of the sample. This value is defined as IDP value between 15-30% raw material can be processed optimally [2].

An IDP value above this limit indicated that the wheat was overheated and, as a result, insufficient inactivation of its nutrients.

4. A decrease in the IDP index below 15% was observed to indicate excessive heating of the raw material and excessive protein denaturation.

In this experiment, the comparative effectiveness of the combined method of heat supply and IR radiation was carried out during the hydrothermal treatment of wheat seeds of the "Pahlovon" variety of wheat.

The experiments were carried out in two ways and the indicators between them were different:

- Using a combined method, an electric heater (EI) was implemented to heat the grain layer in the amount of 2.0 kW from above and 0.5 kW from below;

- The second processing method used only 2.0 kW IR radiation of the upper layers;

- Wheat was pre-moistened to optimal moisture (20-22%) for 10 minutes at room temperature;

Duration of soaking for "Pahlovon" variety of wheat was determined experimentally. After processing the wheat at high temperature, the tempering stage was performed - the moistened grain was kept in a heat-insulated container for 15 minutes.

Studies were conducted according to the scheme presented in Table 1.

The data shown in Table 1 show that with the combined method of providing energy to wheat, the heating rate was much higher than with the option with only IR radiation. It is known

that the quality composition of wheat protein complex containing anti-nutritional factors is highly related to the speed of the high-temperature stage of spatial hydrothermal processing [3].

2. Determination of the optimal ratio of IR radiation and electric heating surface according to the dynamics of temperature changes during heat treatment of wheat.

Table 1

Heating rate of wheat with a combined method of energy supply

Experiments	Energy supply method	Main heating time, sec	The temperature of the main heating, °C	Temperature residual °C
1	Combined method of energy supply	50	100	94
2		60	120	97
3		70	139	96
4		80	145	96
5		90	160	110
6	IR radiation	70	120	90
7		80	135	100
8		90	130	100
9		100	140	105

In order to eliminate the disadvantages of micronization of wheat, which consists of high losses of thermal energy due to the inability to provide sufficient heat during the micronization process, and this leads to incorrect heating, the option of heating with IR radiation from above and with an electric heating surface from below was also used as an experiment.

In order to determine the optimal power ratio of IR radiation and electric heating surface, they were selected, including: 10%:90%, 20%:80%, 30%:70%, 40%:60%, 50%:50%.

Moistening of the grain was also carried out up to 18%, keeping time in a heat-insulated container was carried out for 15 minutes. The power for IR radiation was supplied separately with the help of a circuit rectifier and an electric heating surface and was monitored according to the ammeter and voltmeter indicators.

If the temperature dynamics in the top, bottom and center of the grain are the same, the power ratio is considered positive, that is, successful. The time is measured until the temperature reaches 130°C.

According to the results of the experiment, the optimal ratio of IR radiation and electric heating surface for urease was determined.

3. Determination of the influence of grain heating with IR radiation and combined heat and energy supply on the index of protein dispersion in wheat grain. According to the previously obtained data, it was found that the combined processing method has an advantage over micronization in the form of shorter processing time with equal total power. To determine the effect of heating duration on the protein dispersion index, experiments were conducted as follows.

a) Wheat grain was weighed until equal weights were obtained and the moisture content was moistened to 18%. With respect to the known power of IR radiation and the electric heating surface, it was adapted to the total power of the mock-up using a two-circuit rectifier. Intensive heat treatment was carried out until the temperature reached 130;

b) The dynamics of temperature changes were recorded at intervals of 5 seconds. Heating IR radiation and combined heat treatment were performed sequentially, with equal total power;

c) After that, the wheat grain was poured into a heat-insulated container, where the tempering process took place for 15 minutes;

g) Processed samples were sent to a chemical laboratory to determine urease activity and protein dispersion index. The results of the experiment were presented by researchers, candidate of biological sciences N. The protein dispersion index for IR radiation and combined heating was compared with the determined data by A. Votnovskaya [4].

In the mode of heating with IR radiation, the results show that in both variants of the experiment, the curves of urease activity during heat treatment differed at the beginning of a sharp decrease in the level of AU, maintaining the characteristic of dispersion. Thus, when wheat was heated only by IR radiation from above, the AU did not change for 80 seconds and by the end of this period had a value of 212 ΔpH from an initial level of 2.11 ΔpH . After only 90 seconds there is a drop to a value of 1.85 ϕ , followed by a sharp drop of 10 ϕ in the next 0.66 seconds of heating. It should be noted that the optimal level of urease activity was not reached during the studied period. The decrease in urease activity in the combined heating mode method started after about 60 seconds of heating, in which it reached 1.72 ΔpH , after 0.95 seconds of heating up to 80 ΔpH , it quickly decreased to 0.1 ΔpH at 80 seconds of heat treatment. These data show that the combined method of top and bottom heat supply with the same total heat power (2.0 kW) and initial moisture level of wheat provided faster inhibition of anti-nutritional factors than simultaneous IR-irradiation.

Figure 1 shows the dynamics of changes in the protein dispersion index (DPI) in wheat according to the time of high temperature exposure to the studied methods of hydrothermal processing of wheat.

Figure 1. The influence of time of thermal exposure on the dynamics of urease activity (AU) in "Paxlavon" wheat variety

Heating in IR radiation:

The graph shown in Fig. 1 shows that in both versions of the experiment, the curves of changes in urease activity during heat treatment differed at the time of the beginning of a sharp decrease in the level of AU, maintaining the characteristic of dispersion; 2. When wheat grain is heated from above with only IR radiation, the AU does not change for 80 seconds, and by the end of this period it has a value of 2.12 ΔpH from an initial level of 2.11 ΔpH , and only after 90 seconds there is a decrease to a value of 1.85 ΔpH , the next 0 A sharp drop of 10 ΔpH is observed at 66 seconds of heating.

It should be noted that the optimal level of urease activity was not reached during the studied period.

Combined heating:

In the variant of the combined energy supply method, the urease activity decreased to 1.72 ΔpH after about 60 seconds of heating, to 80 ΔpH after 0.95 seconds of heating, and quickly decreased to 0.1 ΔpH in the 80th second of heat treatment;

These data show that the same overall power of heat (2.0 kW) and the same level of initial moisture composition of wheat are observed, the combined method of heat supply from above and below simultaneously reduce the effect of anti-nutritional factors on protein dispersion index compared to IR radiation from above.

Figure 2 shows the dynamics of changes in the protein dispersion index (DPI) in wheat depending on the time of high temperature exposure to the studied methods of hydrothermal processing of wheat.

Figure 2. Effect of thermal exposure time on the dynamics of protein dispersion index (IDP) in wheat

As can be seen in Fig. 2, in the experimental variant where the heating was provided in a combined manner, with the same power source, the decrease in IDP occurred equally with the heating. This indicator reached the optimal value after 80 seconds of heating at a humidity of -18.57%. At the same time, in the case where the main heating was carried out only by IR lamps from above, the graph of the dependence of the IDP on the heating time was represented by a broken line. This shows that heating wheat during processing in this way does not ensure the

uniformity of the heating process. That is, the uniformity of the processes helps regulate the hydrothermal processing of wheat. It was observed that the optimal value of 22.8% was achieved after 90 seconds of heating in the IR radiation option, which was found to be 10 seconds more than the combined option with heat supply.

During the subsequent heating (for 90 seconds in the K option and 100 seconds in the IR option), protein denaturation in wheat probably goes directly from the stage of changing the protein structure to the stage of protein loss. This is a secondary increase in IDP (up to 27.08% in the K variant and 39.4% in the IK variant), which indicates an increase in the content of low molecular weight nitrogenous substances in processed wheat. In conclusion, it can be noted that the optimal result of hydrothermal treatment using IR radiation for heating, other things being equal, was not obtained even after 100 seconds of exposure. This indicates that the combined method of heat supply during hydrothermal processing of "Pahlovon" wheat at 18-20% humidity was found to be more economical than IR radiation.

Results of an experimental study of the energy parameters of the energy supply system with infrared radiation and combined heating of wheat grain. The calculation results showed that with two-way heating of the wheat grain on its surface at a temperature of 110-130 °C, the temperature in the center of the grain does not differ significantly from the surface temperature (3-5), but the entire grain mass (including the center) was unevenly heated. Research results 2 - is presented in the following table.

IR radiation			Combination heating				
t_t	120	130	145	t_t	107	115	125
t_p	50,6	54	61	t_p	105	11,5	120
t_{orr}	85	93	95	t_{orr}	103	112	115

t_t temperature of the upper layer of the grain,

t_p the temperature of the lower grain layer,

t_{orr} the temperature of the layer between the grains,

Experimental studies have shown that (Fig. 2) with combined heating of wheat grain, the temperature in the initial period is 20°C, and at the end of heating, the temperature is increased to 130°C, the difference between them was observed to be around 3-5°C.

Calculations of heating with one-way infrared light showed that the temperature difference between the heated and unheated surface reaches 30-40 °C. Uneven heating of the interior of the grain does not allow to reduce the level of urease to normalized values [5].

In this case, it is possible to reduce the level of urease only by increasing the temperature to 140-150 °C and increasing the heating time of the grain. However, it has been observed that the quality of processed wheat deteriorates and its consumption properties decrease. In addition, in order to clarify the calculation results, experimental studies were conducted on heating wheat to determine the temperature on the upper, lower surface and in the center of the grain. It can be concluded that high-quality heat treatment of wheat grain can be ensured only by heating with high temperature [6,7]. It was observed that uneven heating of the grain due to one-way infrared radiation was around 50 °C. (Fig. 2-3). In order to reach 130 °C in the center of the grain, it is necessary to increase the heat flow density and heat the grain shell to 160°C, at such a temperature the grain shell begins to burn and the processing quality decreases. In order to introduce the energy supply system with combined heating of wheat grain, the task is to determine heat flows from infrared sources and electric heaters. The process of heating wheat grain in a combined heating

workplace is complex and includes: It is heated by convection from IR sources and electric heating surface (EI), heat transfer from EI by conduction, infrared radiation, reflection, absorption, etc.

5. Conclusion: The use of combined heating of wheat allows to apply the optimal mode of heat treatment (120-130 °C) with uniform heating of the outer and inner parts of the grain, which preserves the high quality of the processed wheat grain and removes anti-nutrients. In addition, double heating reduces the time of heat treatment and, as a result, increases the productivity of the device by 1.4 times and reduces energy consumption by 26.4%:

The ratio of heat flow to the value of N is important in the design of energy supply systems for heat treatment of wheat. This is confirmed by the results of theoretical and experimental studies, the deviation is 11%, which is very acceptable for practical calculations;

The results of experimental studies proved that in order to remove harmful substances, it is necessary to heat the grain in the workplace to a temperature of 130 °C with the combined heating of wheat grains. This means that the temperature is not lower than 90-95 °C and the level of urease activity is not lower than normalized 0.2-0.3 ΔpH and the level of urease activity is normalized 0.2-0.3

As a result of a multifactorial experiment on the study of the energy parameters of the energy supply system with combined heating of wheat grain, an equation describing the interaction of the relative density of heat flows with the duration of heating up to a certain temperature was created. The minimum heating duration was achieved by the following ratio of relative heat fluxes: 70% - IR radiation source from above and 30% - electric heating from below;

A multi-factor experiment to study the parameters of wheat grain heating using energy supply system with combined heating to remove harmful substances: the initial moisture content of wheat grain is 18-20%, the duration of combined heating is 70 seconds, the duration of temperature training is 15 minutes was determined.

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